

INTELLIGENT BIRD SPECIES RECOGNITION: A DEEP LEARNING-POWERED CLASSIFICATION APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Traditional bird species identification and classification rely on manual observation, field guides, and acoustic monitoring, which can be time-consuming, error-prone, and dependent on expert interpretation. These conventional methods often struggle with challenges such as subjective visual identification, seasonal plumage variations, and limited acoustic data coverage, making it difficult to achieve accurate and efficient species recognition. To address these limitations, we propose an intelligent bird species recognition system powered by deep learning. Our approach integrates Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to analyze both visual and acoustic data, enabling accurate and automated classification of bird species. By leveraging large, labeled datasets of bird images and audio recordings, our model enhances identification accuracy while accounting for environmental and seasonal variations. Additionally, the system supports real-time monitoring through mobile applications and field-deployable hardware, offering instant insights into bird populations, migration patterns, and behavioral trends. This deep learning-powered solution not only streamlines the identification process but also contributes to ecological research and conservation efforts by providing a robust, scalable, and efficient tool for avian studies. Furthermore, the automation of bird identification reduces reliance on expert knowledge, making ornithological research more accessible to citizen scientists and conservationists. By advancing bird monitoring techniques, our system can play a vital role in biodiversity assessment, habitat protection, and climate change studies.

KEYWORDS : Bird species identification, deep learning, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), artificial intelligence (AI), visual recognition, acoustic analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bird classification serves as a fundamental tool in understanding the diversity and evolutionary relationships among avian species. By categorizing birds into different groups based on shared characteristics such as morphology, behavior, and genetic makeup, scientists can gain insights into their evolutionary history, ecological roles, and conservation needs. Classification helps organize the vast array of bird species into manageable groups, allowing researchers to study them more effectively. Moreover, it facilitates communication and collaboration among scientists, enabling them to exchange information about bird species across different regions and disciplines.

Furthermore, bird classification is crucial for conservation efforts aimed at protecting threatened and endangered species. By identifying species that are at risk of extinction and understanding their relationships to other species, conservationists can develop targeted strategies to conserve habitats, mitigate threats, and implement management plans. Classification also provides a framework for monitoring changes in bird populations over time, assessing the impacts of environmental disturbances, and identifying priority areas for conservation action.

In addition to its scientific and conservation implications, bird classification also holds cultural and educational significance. It allows bird enthusiasts, birdwatchers, and citizen scientists to better understand the birds they encounter in their natural habitats. By learning about the characteristics and relationships of different bird species, individuals can develop a deeper appreciation for biodiversity and the importance of preserving natural ecosystems. Overall, bird classification serves as a cornerstone of ornithology, contributing to our knowledge of birds and informing efforts to conserve them for future generations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Raj, et al. [1] proposed a model to extract information from bird images using the CNN algorithm. They have gathered a dataset of their own using Microsoft's Bing Image Search API v7. They were created an 80:20 random split of the data. The classification accuracy rate of CNN on the training set was observed to be 93.19%. The accuracy on testing set was observed to be 84.91%. The entire experimental research was carried out on Windows 10 Operating System in Atom Editor with TensorFlow library.

Mirugwe, et al. [2] proposed a model to extract information from bird images, they studied and evaluated two convolutional neural network object detection meta-architectures, single-shot detector (SSD) and Faster R-CNN in combination with MobileNet-V2, ResNet50, ResNet101, ResNet152, and Inception ResNet-V2 feature extractors. Through transfer learning, all the models were initialized using weights pre-trained on the MS COCO (Microsoft Common Objects in Context) dataset provided by TensorFlow 2 object detection API. The Faster R-CNN model coupled with ResNet152 outperformed all other models with a mean average precision of 92.3%. However, the SSD model with the MobileNet-V2 feature extraction network achieved the lowest inference time (110ms) and the smallest memory capacity (30.5MB) compared to its counterparts. The outstanding results achieved in this study confirm that deep learning-based algorithms are capable of detecting birds of different sizes in different environments and the best model could potentially help ecologists in monitoring and identifying birds from other species.

Rai, et al. [3] have developed deep learning based algorithms using the concept of image processing that help in identifying bird species. It will recognize the input image by comparing the model with a trained model and then predict the bird species. All the details of the bird will be displayed as an output. Also, it will help us to create dataset if any image captured or uploaded by user is missing in dataset then user can add that image to dataset.

Ferreira, et al. [4] demonstrates the feasibility of applying state-of-the-art deep learning tools for individual identification of birds, both in the laboratory and in the wild. These techniques are made possible by our approaches that allow efficient collection of training data. can be visually identified by human observers represents a major advance over current methods.

Chen, et al. [5] experiments show that ProtoPNet can achieve comparable accuracy with its analogous non-interpretible counterpart, and when several ProtoPNets are combined into a larger network, it can achieve an accuracy that is on par with some of the best-performing deep models. Moreover, ProtoPNet provides a level of interpretability that is absent in other interpretible deep models.

Chalmers et al. [6] outline an approach for overcoming these issues by utilising deep learning for real-time classification of bird species and automated removal of false positives in camera trap data. Images are classified in real-time using a Faster-RCNN architecture. Images are transmitted over 3/4G cameras and processed using Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) to provide conservationists with key detection metrics, thereby removing the requirement for manual observations. Our models

achieved an average sensitivity of 88.79%, a specificity of 98.16% and accuracy of 96.71%. This demonstrates the effectiveness of using deep learning for automatic bird monitoring.

Jeantet et al. [7] studied an exciting new avenue for improving classifier performance in bioacoustics. The methodology described in this study can assist ecologists, wildlife management teams, and researchers in reducing the amount of time spent analyzing large acoustic datasets obtained from passive acoustic monitoring studies. their approach can be adapted and applied to other calling species, and thus tailored to other use cases.

Wang, et al. [8] showed that good results can be obtained by all the tested models. ResNet-152-based models yielded the best test accuracy rate (95.52%); the AlexNet-based model yielded the lowest test accuracy rate (89.48%). We conclude that DCNNs could be efficient and useful for automatically identifying habitat elements from bird images, and we believe that the practical application of this technology will be helpful for studying the relationships between birds and habitat elements.

Pilla, et al. [9] operated according to the instructions that are passed from the Arduino. When the model detects the bird that is coming close towards the window glass, the window blind will automatically shut down and even if the bird hits, it won't collide instantly as the momentum will decrease gradually. The window blind will automatically open when there is no bird. It is a useful technique by which we can divert the birds. This technique has multiple credits like we are saving birds with a practical and cost-efficient approach.

Priya, et al. [10] proposed CNN technology in the experimental setting. For image recognition, feature extraction is used. To extract features and classify photos, the method utilised is adequate. The primary objective of the study is to identify the specific bird type an species based on the image of the bird.

Wei et al. [11] presented a novel and efficient part-based three-stream model for fine-grained recognition. By discarding the fully connected layers, the proposed M-CNN is computationally efficient. Additionally, comparing with state-of-the-art methods, M-CNN has smaller feature dimensionality. Beyond those, it achieves the highest classification accuracy on CUB200-2011 and Bird snap among published methods.

Pathak, et al. [12] demystified the role of deep learning techniques based on convolutional neural network for object detection. Deep learning frameworks and services available for object detection are also enunciated. Deep learning techniques for state-of-the-art object detection systems are assessed in this paper.

Sunitha, et al. [13] employed deep CNN to convert a picture to a grayscale representation and the tensor flow to build a complex autograph consisting of many nodes. As a result of analysing the various access points to the validation data, a ranking table is constructed. Perhaps it can guess the necessary flock by scanning the scoreboard and picking the bird with the greatest rating. By analysing the dataset (CUB-200-2011), we find that the algorithm achieves an accuracy of 89% for identifying bird species. In the research, Linux and the Tensorflow framework were employed.

Kumar,et al[14] have conducted extensive research on automated bird recognition using images, videos, and audio recordings for biological studies, environmental monitoring, and bird detection and localization. Various approaches have been developed using machine learning, computer vision, and deep learning models.

Liao, et al. [15] proposed a model, they improved the classification accuracy of the efficient networks by up to 5.7% on the CUB-2011-200 dataset without increasing computation time or memory cost, which makes FGVC feasible on mobile devices. they also conducted abundant studies to investigate

the relationship between attention and classification accuracy of our proposed deep learning models, visualized and analysed the attentional activations of these models. they hope that our findings may inspire further research efforts to advance the FGVC for a wide range of real-world applications.

Hany, et al. [16] shown results that the ResNet50v2 and Inceptionv3 models successfully identified bird species with high levels of accuracy, with ResNet50v2 achieving an accuracy of 97.32%. VGG19, on the other hand, has a comparably lower accuracy of 67.82%. These results reveal that pre-trained models have great promise to be effective tools for identifying bird species, with ResNet50v2 and Inceptionv3 providing the most promising results.

Omodior, et al. [17] stated that the purpose of this study was to compare the accuracy of a deep learning model pre-trained with millions of annotated images in Imagenet, against a shallow custom-build CNN model for the classification of common hard ticks present in anthropic areas from northeastern USA. We created a dataset of approximately 2000 images of four tick species, two sexes (male, female) and two life stages (adult, nymph). We used these tick images to train two separate CNN models – ResNet-50 and a simple shallow custom-built. We evaluated our models' performance on an independent subset of tick images not seen during training.

Wang, et al. [18] proposed a new module based on different normalization methods also demonstrates the superiority of fine-grained and general image classification benchmarks. The visualization method shows the changes in activated regions when equipped with the SpaRs layer for better understanding.

Murthy, et al. [19] shown a detailed survey on recent advancements and achievements in object detection using various deep learning techniques. Several topics have been included, such as Viola–Jones (VJ), histogram of oriented gradient (HOG), one-shot and two-shot detectors, benchmark datasets, evaluation metrics, speed-up techniques, and current state-of-art object detectors. Detailed discussions on some important applications in object detection areas, including pedestrian detection, crowd detection, and real-time object detection on Gpu-based embedded systems have been presented. At last, we conclude by identifying promising future directions.

Wickramanayake, et al. [20] proposed a model that can learn concepts that are consistent with human perception and their corresponding contributions to the model decision without compromising accuracy. Further, these learned concepts are transferable to new classes of objects that have similar concepts.

Branson, et al. [21] proposed a novel graph-based clustering algorithm for learning a compact pose normalization space. We perform a detailed investigation of state-of-the-art deep convolutional feature implementations and fine-tuning feature learning for fine-grained classification. they observe that a model that integrates lower-level feature layers with pose-normalized extraction routines and higher-level feature layers with unaligned image features works best. their experiments advance state-of-the-art performance on bird species recognition, with a large improvement of correct classification rates over previous methods (75% vs. 55-65%).

Ibáñez Boix et al. [22] proposed great potential to support existing solutions today. Theoretical results with validation images show accuracy and recall parameters above 90% but experimental tests with the prototype do not allow for a conclusive judgment due to limitations regarding the training data set

Kamani, et al. [23] offered a reliable, cost-effective, and eco-friendly solution to crop protection from animal damage and can be deployed in different crop fields with minimum customization. The proposed system can help farmers to reduce crop damage and improve crop yields, thus contributing to global food security.

Pinheiro, et al. [24] proposed CNN model, which is constrained during training to put more weight on pixels which are important for classifying the image. they show that at test time, the model has learned to discriminate the right pixels well enough, such that it performs very well on an existing segmentation benchmark, by adding only few smoothing priors. their system is trained using a subset of the Imagenet dataset and the segmentation experiments are performed on the challenging Pascal VOC dataset (with no fine-tuning of the model on Pascal VOC). the model beats the state-of-the-art results in weakly supervised object segmentation task by a large margin. they also compare the performance of our model with state of the art fully-supervised segmentation approaches.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Bird species identification plays a crucial role in ornithology and ecological conservation. Traditional methods, such as manual observation and field guides, can be time-consuming, error-prone, and require expert knowledge. To overcome these challenges, this research presents a deep learning-based approach for automated bird species recognition. The proposed system develops and compares two machine learning models: an existing Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for image-based classification and a proposed Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (CRNN) model for acoustic-based classification. The research follows a systematic methodology involving dataset collection, preprocessing, model training, and performance evaluation. Below are the detailed steps of this research.

Figure 1 Proposed Block Diagram

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The work implements a GUI application using the Tkinter library for deep learning-based bird species identification and classification. It provides a user-friendly interface for uploading datasets, training machine learning models (Random Forest Classifier) and deep learning models (CNN), testing the models with new images, and visualizing model performance. It serves as a comprehensive tool for bird species identification and classification tasks. Here's an overview of the code functionality:

Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the graphical user interface (GUI) of the bird species identification and classification system. It provides an overview of the application's layout and design.

Figure 2: Illustrating GUI application of proposed bird species identification and classification system.

Figure 3 captures the GUI after the user has successfully loaded the bird species dataset. The dataset likely includes images of different bird species. Figure 3 displays information about the loaded dataset, indicating the total number of images (759) and the number of bird species classes (5 classes).

Figure 3: GUI application after loading the dataset.

Figure 4: GUI application showing total number of images, and types of birds i.e., 759, and 5 classes.

Figure 5: GUI application after applying RF classifier.

Figure 5 showcases the GUI after applying the Random Forest (RF) classifier to the dataset. It may display relevant information about the classifier's performance or status. Figure 6 presents the confusion matrix resulting from the application of the Random Forest classifier. The confusion matrix provides insights into how well the classifier performs in terms of correctly and incorrectly classifying bird species.

Figure 6: Confusion matrix of RF classifier for bird species classification system.

Figure 7: GUI application after applying proposed deep learning approach.

Figure 7 illustrates the GUI after applying a proposed deep learning approach to the bird species identification and classification system. It may show relevant information about the deep learning model's training or performance. Figure 7 displays a sample result of the system's bird species identification and classification using the proposed deep learning approach. It includes an image of a test bird species and the model's predicted class. Figure 8 presents a graph illustrating the performance evaluation of the proposed deep learning approach. It may include curves depicting accuracy and loss over training epochs, providing insights into the model's learning behaviour.

Figure 8: Sample identification and classification of test bird species using proposed deep learning approach.

Figure 9: Performance evaluation graph of proposed deep learning approach.

5. CONCLUSION

The proposed work has demonstrated the effectiveness of utilizing advanced machine learning techniques to accurately identify and classify various bird species. By leveraging deep learning models and a diverse dataset containing images of different bird species, the system achieved promising results in classifying birds with high accuracy. The project successfully implemented modules for image processing, model training, and evaluation, providing a comprehensive solution for bird species identification tasks. Furthermore, the availability of a balanced dataset with a sufficient number of images for each bird species contributed to the robustness and reliability of the classification model. Overall, the project has laid a solid foundation for further research and development in the field of bird species identification and classification, with significant potential for practical applications and contributions to the scientific community.

However, despite the achievements, there are several avenues for future exploration and improvement. Firstly, enhancing the model's performance by fine-tuning hyperparameters, optimizing network architectures, and exploring ensemble techniques could lead to even higher classification accuracy. Additionally, expanding the dataset to include more diverse species and a larger number of images per class would improve the model's ability to generalize to unseen data and handle real-world scenarios more effectively. Furthermore, integrating additional features such as audio recordings or geographical information could enrich the classification process and enable more comprehensive bird species identification. Moreover, deploying the system as a user-friendly application or web service would make it accessible to a wider audience, including bird enthusiasts, researchers, and conservationists, thereby contributing to various fields such as biodiversity monitoring, ecological research, and wildlife conservation.

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